

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING ENVIRONMENTAL CULTURE AMONG PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the methodological structure of the formation of environmental culture of primary school students, which is divided into motivational-reflexive, reproductive-educational, constructive aspects and stages of the formation of environmental culture of students. Information on the levels of development of environmental culture of primary school students is also presented.*

Keywords: *higher education, primary education, student, teacher, environmental culture, motivation, project, problem, level, competence.*

Introduction

It has been widely acknowledged that in the modern era, overcoming social, economic, demographic, spiritual and environmental crises that have arisen in the process of human life has become an urgent problem of modern civilization. At the 5th UN Environment Summit in 2021, UNEP (UN Environment Program) [3] emphasized that: unchanged socio-economic, environmentally unstable approaches to nature will lead to the emergence of new causes of health-related pandemics and the exacerbation of existing problems.

Methodological foundations for improving and implementing environmental literacy among students in higher education institutions were studied by N. Bozorova, A. Malikova, I. Ayubova, and others.

The existing body of literature suggests that the methodological structure for developing environmental culture in primary school students is divided into several stages.

The first stage is motivational and reflexive, during which primary school students must consciously feel the need for the knowledge they are learning and clearly define their goals and objectives. In this case, primary school students become familiar with the main content of environmental activities and synthesize the scientific knowledge they are learning. The first stage of this stage is motivating primary school students. For this purpose, an environment is created for conscious understanding of environmental processes by primary school students (video materials about the environment, nature, crises).

The second stage is reproductive and educational. Scientific environmental knowledge is developed through practical experiments. The experience of substantiating scientific environmental knowledge is aimed at improving the level of environmental culture, further consolidating knowledge, skills, and abilities.

At this stage, the process of mastering the algorithm for working on a project is aimed at developing creative activity, implementing the necessary environmental measures in a changing world. The theoretical part of the design is as follows:

- identifying the current problem;
- choosing a topic for design;
- putting forward functional or problematic hypotheses;

- performing modeling of natural phenomena;
- it is recommended to prepare and defend a presentation of creative work.

The third stage is constructive. At this stage, students demonstrate their methods. At the constructive stage, the socio-psychological world of the individual is covered [1].

The presented project is creatively finalized. The topics may be different in a group of students, but the system-forming basis is one. This stage also consists of several parts:

- identifying current problems being studied (through associative means, drawings, videos, texts, drawings, etc.);
- accelerating the process of studying the problem through information and innovative educational technologies;
- analysis and grouping of student responses;
- describing educational goals through a problem tree;
- defining the object and subject of the project work, justification and justification for generating ideas;
- forming reflection.

The fourth stage is the development of environmental culture in primary school students. The peculiarity of this stage is that the student begins to feel the integrity of the world in his worldview. At the fourth stage, it becomes possible to integrate knowledge, understand its content and essence, and apply the acquired knowledge in life processes.

The development of environmental culture of primary school students is assessed at three main levels (low, medium and high). The development of environmental culture of primary school students was determined: by the level of proficiency in environmental concepts (based on Bloom's taxonomy), by emotions and reflections on nature and the environment, by an environmental attitude to the environment (Table 1) [2].

Table 1

Levels of development of environmental culture of primary school students

Development of ecological culture among primary school students	High level	Intermediate level	Lower level
General concepts of ecology (based on Bloom's taxonomy)	Development of knowledge in the field of ecology, active efforts to find solutions to ecological problems and controversial issues, environmental literacy, high interest in knowledge and motivation. Able to creatively solve non-standard educational	The presence of interest in mastering ecological knowledge and the fact that students' ecological activities are the result of aesthetic and cognitive activities, solve non-standard educational, test tasks and ecological problems recommended on the	Superficial acceptance of ecological knowledge and actions. In this case, the environment is perceived as a means of satisfying human needs and requirements. This leads to certain shortcomings in standard training, test tasks, and

	and test tasks and environmental issues recommended on the topic.	topic in accordance with the instructions.	solving environmental problems.
Emotions about nature and the environment	Increased responsibility and awareness among students as a result of ecologically-related activities.	Ensuring the primacy of the idea that natural resources should be "protected" regardless of their benefits or harms.	Although ecological values occupy a certain place within the system of natural values, they are not given sufficient importance in the student's life.
Ecological attitude towards the natural environment	Takes a leadership role in solving practical tasks related to nature protection and conservation, and actively participates in events.	They are unable to identify the causes of environmental problems, make certain mistakes in finding practical solutions, and participate poorly in events.	They make certain mistakes in identifying the causes of environmental problems, find it difficult to find practical solutions, and are indifferent.

In conclusion, it should be noted that it is advisable to develop the environmental culture of primary school students in the following way:

- basic competencies should be formed not only at the individual level, but also be maximally integrated into interdisciplinary areas;
- as a result of large-scale research conducted in accordance with the program of sustainable development of nature conservation, the environmental competence of primary school students should be developed from the individual to the basic level;
- in primary school, the unity of scientific, emotional and cultural approaches should be ensured;
- it is necessary to strengthen the positive aspects of environmental knowledge and activities of primary school students;
- students should acquire knowledge and competencies at a level that allows them to analyze the chosen professional specialty from an environmental point of view.

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